

DELIVERABLE

**2023-DL.3.1.2: DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN HUSBANDRY SYSTEMS USED FOR
TURKEY FARMING IN EUROPE**

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1. Introduction

The EU turkey meat sector produces around 1,8 million tons of turkey meat every year representing the second largest producer worldwide after the USA.

Turkeys represent 12.7% of the total poultry meat production in the EU (figure 1, DG Agri-2023).

Figure 1. EU production of poultry meat (2023). Credit to EU Commission.

According to a survey conducted by the European Commission, the annual turkey meat production has remained rather stable since 2019. A production peak of 2,000 thousand tons during 2020 was followed by a slight decrease during 2021, with the lowest production reached during 2022, an overall increase of 3.7% is expected during 2023 and a further slight increase of 0.9% in 2024 (figure 2).

Figure 2. Experts EU27 production forecast on poultry and rabbit (updated to 19 October 2023). Credit to EU Commission.

Data from European Commission show that the 5 major turkey producing countries are: Poland, Germany, Italy, France and Spain. During 2023, these countries will produce around 81.9% of the total EU turkey meat production (table 1). According to experts' forecast, among the major producing countries, Poland and Germany are likely to increase production in 2024, while production in the others will remain rather stable.

Table 1. Turkey production in EU (thousand tonnes; expert forecast autumn 2023). Credit to EU Commission

EU thousand tonnes production of turkey (expert forecast Autumn 2023)			
EU Member State	2022	2023	2024
Poland	425,1	433,0	440,0
Germany	335,0	335,0	340,0
Italy	219,0	275,0	275,0
France	252,0	235,4	235,4
Spain	197,8	217,6	217,6
Hungary	103,0	97,3	97,5
Portugal	45,6	53,0	53,0
Ireland	32,5	32,0	32,5
Netherland	28,0	28,0	28,0
Austria	21,6	21,6	21,6
Romania	20,0	17,0	20,0
Croatia	18,0	18,0	18,0
Greece	14,1	14,1	14,1
Czech Republic	10,0	10,0	10,0
Finland	8,8	9,0	9,1
Belgium	6,2	6,8	6,8
Slovenia	5,5	5,8	5,8
Lithuania	5,5	5,5	5,5
Sweden	5,0	5,0	5,0
Denmark	5,1	4,2	4,5
Slovakia	3,0	3,0	3,0
Cyprus	0,1	0,1	0,1
TOTAL	1761,0	1826,6	1842,6

Despite the huge number of animals involved, in the EU keeping turkeys is not specifically regulated but only covered by Council Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes. Legal requirements provided by the general recommendations of Council Directive 98/58/EC are very vague, for which reason husbandry systems and rearing conditions are mainly based on industry guidelines.

The purpose of this deliverable is to give insight into the main features of turkey farming in Europe, which can aid in identifying the major welfare risks in turkey production and support the drafting of future specific legislation on the rearing of turkeys.

The categories of turkeys considered in this deliverable are the following;

- Turkey poults which means young turkeys from hatch until the end of the brooding period.
- Commercial turkeys or broiler turkeys, which means turkeys raised for meat production.
- Turkey breeders which means turkeys kept for the production of eggs from which the commercial turkeys hatch.

2. Methods

For the purpose of this deliverable, a questionnaire on the main characteristics of the turkey farming sector was developed based on expert knowledge and was composed of 21 questions (table 2).

Table 2. Questionnaire submitted to the members of the Poultry Veterinary Study Group of the EU.

1	N° turkeys produced annually in your country
2	N° of integrations producing turkeys
3	Does your country import turkeys for slaughter? From where?
4	Does your country export turkeys for slaughter? To where?
5	How many slaughter plants are there in your country?
6	For each, please indicate the number of birds slaughtered weekly and the stunning system used
7	N° of commercial turkey farms in your country
8	N° of turkey breeder farms in your country
9	N° of hatcheries in your country
10	N° of GP farms in your country
11	Strain type reared:
12	Strain size reared:
13	Please fill in average age and average weight at slaughter in your country:
14	Please indicate the farming systems in use in your country, with relative stocking densities (kg/m ²)
15	Is thinning carried out?

16	Birds are moved from brooding to rearing house
17	Birds are kept in the same building through lifetime
18	Is debeaking carried out?
19	Are mutilations practiced?
20	What types of litter are used?
21	Are enrichments used?
22	If yes, please describe which kind of enrichments and how are they used:

N°: number.

The questionnaire was then submitted to the members of the Poultry Veterinary Study Group of the EU, a formally constituted group of poultry veterinarians with practical responsibilities for health aspects of European poultry production which has existed for over 50 years <https://www.pvsgeu.org/>. Members of the PVSGEU belong to EU member states, Norway, Switzerland and Great Britain. Experts of the group from 18 countries responded to the survey: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain (GB), Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland. Although GB is no longer an EU member state, it was decided to consider also this country in view of its involvement in the turkey EU market and in particular in the breeder sector.

Data collected were merged in an excel sheet, divided by country. Description of the main characteristics of the farming systems in European countries was then drafted based on expert knowledge and integrated with data collected in the survey.

3. Results

3.1 Turkey production in the Europe

The European turkey producing countries rear mainly heavy or medium/heavy birds of two main commercial breeding companies: Aviagen and Hybrid (Table 7).

In Europe, as well as in other industrialised regions, turkeys are produced in vertically integrated production systems. However, the level of integration may differ between countries, but also within the same country. In Germany for instance, out of the 4 operating turkey integrations, 1 company is totally integrated while the other 3 do not control the entire production chain. The timing and number of poults hatched and delivered to the farms and the market age birds dispatched from farms to the slaughterhouses follow a strict time schedule. This allows optimum utilisation of facilities at hatchery, farm, slaughter and transport level. Intensive turkey production in Europe is characterised by very large holdings, indoor rearing, high stocking densities and fast growth rates. This production model accounts for over 90% of the turkey production in Europe. Standard commercial turkey barns in Europe have an average surface of one thousand (1,000) m² and conventional farms usually hold one to six barns housing from six thousand (6,000) to thirty thousand (30,000) birds.

As shown in table 3, among European countries, Germany has the largest number of commercial farms (around 950) followed by Italy (around 850), Poland (around 700) and Spain (around 650). The survey reports only the number of farms without detailing the number of barns per farm. Hungary has the largest number of integrations, while some major turkey meat producing countries, like Poland and France, have only one or two very large integrations.

Great Britain and France are the only two countries which have grandparent (GP) farms on their territory. All the main producing countries have breeder farms although the exact figures for France have not been provided.

Table 3. Survey results on the number of integrations, commercial farms, breeder farms, GP farms and hatcheries.

Country	N° of integrations	N° of commercial farms	N° of breeder farms	N° of GP farms	N° of hatcheries
Austria	3	190	0	0	1
Belgium	1	25	0	0	1
Bulgaria	2	2	0	2	3
Cyprus	4	0*	0	0	0
Denmark	0	13	0	0	0
Finland	1	32	6	0	1
France	2	Unknown	Unknown	14	5
Germany	4	950	30	0	8
Great Britain	7	2500**	250*	20	5
Hungary	8-10	215	6	0	6
Italy	4	850	30	0	4
Netherlands	0	30	0	0	0
Norway	2	46	2	0	2
Poland	1	700	30	0	5
Romania	1	10	0	0	3
Spain	6	650***	22	0	5
Sweden	Unknown	10	7	0	1
Switzerland	2	45	0	0	1
Total	50	3.118	131	36	51

N°: number. *Reared in broiler farms only during the Christmas period **Referred to registered flocks, not farms. *** Officially 1800, but 650 for industrial production.

The results of the survey, showed in table 4, confirm that the five largest producing European countries are Poland, France, Spain, Italy and Germany.

Poland and Germany (8,000,000 birds) are the only countries in Europe that import turkeys. However, no precise numbers have been obtained from Poland. The European countries that export turkeys are Poland (no detailed data), Hungary (1,700,000), Netherlands (1,300,000), Denmark (600,000) and Belgium (300,000).

Table 4. Survey results on the number of turkeys produced, imported and exported.

Country	N° turkeys produced annually	Turkeys imported for slaughter	From where	Turkeys exported for slaughter	To where
Austria	1.800.000	No		Yes	DE,PL
Belgium	1.000.000	No		300.000	DE
Bulgaria	8.000	No		No	
Cyprus	25.000	No		No	
Denmark	600.000	No		600.000	DE
Finland	936.850	No		No	
France	32.000.000	No		Yes	DE
Germany	24.500.000	8.000.000	CZ,PL,HG,DK,NL,BL,FR,AU	Sporadically	PL
Great Britain	14.000.000	No		No	
Hungary	7.418.000	No		1.700.000	DE,PL
Italy	28.000.000	No		No	
Netherlands	1.500.000	No		1.300.000	DE
Norway	1.000.000	No		No	
Poland	40.000.000	Yes	LT,DE	Yes	EU,EB,Middle East, Africa
Romania	2.800.000	No		No	
Spain	30.000.000	No		No	
Sweden	500.000	No		No	
Switzerland	275.000	No		No	
Total	186.362.850	8.000.000		3.900.000	

N°: number.

3.2 Production cycle of turkeys

3.2.1 Day-old poults

Turkey poults are hatched in hatcheries, the number and distribution of the hatcheries within the member states are reported in table 3. Among European countries, Germany has the largest number of hatcheries (8) followed by Hungary (6), France, Poland and Spain (5).

Table 5. European trends in the poult trade, Millions (2015-2022). Credit to AVEC.

Major European Markets Commercial Poult Placements, Millions (2015 - 2022)								
Country	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Poland	41,3	42,9	46,2	47,6	51,1	46,0	42,4	41,0
France	49,5	47,2	45,0	42,2	40,9	40,3	35,8	31,2
Spain	21,0	22,0	24,0	28,0	30,0	29,0	29,0	29,0
Germany	30,7	30,7	29,0	28,0	28,4	27,2	26,2	24,8
Italy	30,0	30,0	30,0	30,0	30,0	29,0	27,1	23,0
Hungary	8,0	8,0	8,0	7,5	7,5	7,0	7,5	7,5
Romania	5,5	5,0	4,8	4,4	4,0	3,5	3,5	3,5
Ukraine	2,0	2,0	2,3	2,6	2,7	2,8	3,0	2,9
Austria	1,8	1,8	1,9	1,8	1,6	1,8	2,0	2,1
Croatia	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5
Finland	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
Norway	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
Czech Republic	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6	0,6	0,6
Sweden	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
Slovenia	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,5	0,5
Slovakia	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,3
TOTAL	193,2	192,9	194,5	195,4	201,0	192,1	181,9	170,4

According to Avec ([Association of Poultry Processors and Poultry Trade in the EU countries \(avec-poultry.eu\)](http://Association of Poultry Processors and Poultry Trade in the EU countries (avec-poultry.eu))), around 200 million poult are placed on farm in Europe each year (table 5).

Eggs are set in incubators for 25 days of incubation after which they are transferred to hatching chambers where they hatch in approximately 3 days. The range of procedures that the poult go through post-hatch may vary between member states and single hatcheries. These procedures are performed to prepare poult for grow out to avoid high first week mortality and prevent injuries.

Procedures mainly consist in grading, sexing, beak trimming, claw trimming (in countries where these mutilation procedures are permitted) and vaccinations. The results of the survey show that almost all countries perform beak trimming, with laser, on day old poult in the hatchery. Exceptions are Bulgaria, Finland, Norway, Sweden and Switzerland. Furthermore, France, Italy and Great Britain reported to perform claw trimming (microwave claw processing, MCP) on day-old female turkey poult in the hatchery.

Table 6. Survey results about mutilations among European countries.

Country	Debeaking	Other mutilations
Austria	Yes	No
Belgium	Yes	No
Bulgaria	No	No
Cyprus	Yes	No
Denmark	Yes	No
Finland	No	No
France	Yes	Yes (claw trimming for females, wing trimming*)
Germany	Yes (only for commercial production)	No
Great Britain	Yes	Yes (some claw trimming for females and wing tagging)**
Hungary	Yes	No
Italy	Yes	Yes (claw trimming for females)
Netherlands	Yes	No
Norway	No	No
Poland	Yes	No
Romania	Yes	No
Spain	Yes	No
Sweden	No	No
Switzerland	No	No

* Wing trimming only for free range (birds up to 4 kg). ** Wing tagging of breeder stock.

Table 7. Survey results on litter type used in European countries

Country	Litter type
Austria	Wood shavings, wood granulate (start house)
Belgium	Wood shavings, flax mud
Bulgaria	Straw
Cyprus	Wood shavings, straw
Denmark	Wood shavings (start house), straw (growing house)
Finland	Wood shavings, peat
France	Wood shavings, straw
Germany	Wood shavings (start house), straw (growing house), pellet, sunflower and spelt hulls
Great Britain	Wood shavings, straw
Hungary	Wood shavings, straw
Italy	Wood shavings, straw, rice hulls, coconut husk (growing house)
Netherlands	Wood shavings, straw
Norway	Wood shavings
Poland	Wood shavings, straw, straw pellet
Romania	Wood shavings (start house), straw (growing house)
Spain	Wood shavings, straw, rice hulls
Sweden	Wood shavings, straw
Switzerland	Wood shavings, straw

3.2.2 Turkeys for meat production

After hatching, poults are transported directly from the hatchery to the rearing facility and are introduced in a thoroughly sanitised production unit. Turkeys kept for standard meat production are typically raised in all-in/all-out production systems, in indoor free-range facilities (loose house), with bedding material and *ad libitum* access to feed and water. Commercial turkeys in indoor floor housing systems are mostly kept in large-scale buildings with automated feed and water lines. The floor is usually made of concrete and fully covered with substrate. Different types of substrates are used, of which wood shavings, peat, rice hulls and (chopped or pelleted) straw, depending on their availability in the different geographic regions, are most common. From the results of the survey, it appears that the most commonly used litter materials are wood shavings and straw (table 7).

Turkey poults are sex sorted at the hatchery and raised in separate groups, since market age differs between males and females. Poults placed on farm are most commonly kept in brooder rings (spot brooders) for at least the first five days of production in order to provide them with an appropriate environment and keep them close to the heat source, and with easy access to feed and water. Another approach, adopted recently by more and more companies is to place poults in “ambient” brooders, meaning loose house facilities specifically equipped to satisfy the requirements of young poults, without the use of rings or other partitions.

For young turkeys, paper or cardboard egg trays are laid out on the floor area, filled with feed, to promote feed intake during the first days of life. When the birds walk over the paper, feed particles move and trigger the poults to peck. The use of paper also facilitates the differentiation of feed from litter. The water lines consist of bell, troughs or nipple drinkers, specifically designed for poults. Feed is usually offered in round troughs by automated feeder systems; these can be either tubes containing around 40 kg of feed or more commonly pans containing around 1 kg of feed.

Management guides provide information on the special needs and performance goals of the poults placed on farm. As the poults cannot regulate their own body temperature in the first days, the house is heated before arrival and in the first weeks. Environmental temperature should be 28–30° C and 60–70% humidity. As temperature and humidity are strongly correlated, other (higher) temperatures might be applicable in case of different (lower) humidity. The thermal need might also depend on the age of the parental stock, with 1–2°C higher temperatures needed for poults of young flocks. In case of using spot brooding, 32°C should be provided at the edge of the brooders. The most common heaters are gas powered (e.g., radiant heat brooder stove, radiant tube heating).

Conventional production cycles of fast-growing turkeys differ slightly in duration and target body weight, depending on sex and strain of the bird as well as market requirements of the different countries. In Europe basically two categories of commercial turkeys are reared: medium and heavy strains. Out of the 18 responding countries, medium turkeys are typically reared in Belgium, Cyprus, Finland, France, Great Britain, Hungary (but only 10% of the total production), Norway, Sweden and Spain, with different final weight objectives according to internal market preferences.

Heavy turkeys are reared in Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, France (in the case of exported turkeys and particularly the breeders), Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania and Switzerland. Turkeys of the heavy strain reach average market age at 20 weeks in the case of males at 20/21 kg and 15/16 weeks for the females at around 10/11 kg (table 8).

Table 8. Survey answers from turkey experts regarding strain type and size of turkeys, including age and weight at slaughter

Country	Strain type reared	Strain size reared	Age at slaughter (weeks)	Weight at slaughter (kg)
Austria	BUT6; Hybrid converter; novo	Heavy	21/22 (Tom) - 18/19 (Hen)	22/23 (Tom) - 12/13 (Hen)
Belgium	Aviagen PREMIUM - BIG6	Medium	16 (Tom) - 16 (Hen)	15/16 (Tom) - 10/11 (Hen)
Bulgaria	Unknown	Heavy	Unknown	Unknown
Cyprus	Aviagen	Medium	9/10 (Tom) - 11 (Hen)	6,5 (Tom) - 6 (Hen)
Denmark	BUT6 - Hybrid converter; novo	Heavy	21/22 (Tom) - 18/19 (Hen)	22/23 (Tom) - 12/13 (Hen)
Finland	Aviagen	Medium	17 (Tom) - 13/14 (Hen)	17,5 (Tom) - 9,5 (Hen)*
France	Aviagen; Hybrid	Heavy; Medium**	16 (Tom) - 12 (Hen)	15 (Tom) - 7 (Hen)
Germany	BUT6; BUT PREMIUM; TP7; Hybrid converter; novo; AUBURN and BBB (for organic)	Heavy	21/22 (Tom) - 15/16 (Hen)	22/23 (Tom) - 11 (Hen)
Great Britain	Aviagen; Hybrid	Medium	18/19 (Tom) - 11/18 (Hen)	18/19 (Tom) - 7,5 (Hen)***
Hungary	Aviagen; Hybrid	Heavy; Medium	20/21 (Tom) - 15 (Hen)	20/21 (Tom) - 9/9,5 (Hen)****
Italy	Aviagen; Hybrid	Heavy	19/20 (Tom) - 14/15 (Hen)	20/21,5 (Tom) - 9,5/10,5 (Hen)
Netherlands	Aviagen; Hybrid	Heavy	21 (Tom) - 15/16 (Hen)	22/22,5 (Tom) - 10,5/11 (Hen)
Norway	Aviagen	Medium	18,5 (Tom) - 12,5 (Hen)	18,5 (Tom) - 8 (Hen)
Poland	BUT6; Hybrid converter; novo	Heavy	18/19 (Tom) - 14 (Hen)	19/20 (Tom) - 9/10 (Hen)
Romania	BUT6; Hybrid converter	Heavy	17/19 (Tom) - 11/15 (Hen)	18/20 (Tom) - 6,5/10,5 (Hen)
Spain	Aviagen PREMIUM; Hybrid	Medium	18 (Tom) - 14 (Hen)	18 (Tom) - 8,5/9 (Hen)
Sweden	BUT PREMIUM	Medium	17/20 (Tom) - 9/10 (Hen)	17/20 (Tom) - 5 (Hen)
Switzerland	Aviagen; Hybrid	Heavy	18 (Tom); 12 (Hen)	19 (Tom) - 7/8 (Hen)

. *Higher weight than conventional, probably a different feeding management. **France rear heavy strains to export hatching eggs for Germany. ***For Christmas, GB rear some heavier birds (up to 20 kg for males

and 12 for females). ****Medium strain rearing for maximum of 10% of total production. Therefore, in average slaughter, weight medium strains are included.

There are slight differences between countries not only in the strain used but also in management procedures applied and this impacts the stocking densities reached during and at the end of the production cycle. For example, in some systems birds are reared separately as far as sex is concerned in different holdings. Males are housed at 3,5-4 birds/m², while females are housed at 6,5-7,3 birds/m² with a final stocking density of around 60 kg/m² for males and 56 kg/m² for females (lower densities are reached in case of voluntary welfare assessment schemes). In this rearing model, stocking density increases gradually with the growing of the birds during the rearing cycle to reach maximum stocking density just prior to loadout. In other systems, male and female birds are housed on the same production site on the same date and when females (which reach market age earlier than males) are sent to slaughter, it allows the remaining male birds to gain more weight with an increased space allowance, a procedure called 'thinning'. Therefore, in this case the highest stocking density is reached in 2 different periods of the production cycle; before female bird removal (thinning) and at the end of the male production cycle. According to the survey thinning is used by 9 countries out of the 18 that responded (table 9).

Also, the choice of brooding system impacts stocking density, since poults may be housed in brooding barns and later moved to grower houses (brood and move system) or remain in the same building throughout the production cycle. In the brood and move system (see table 9), the birds will reach a high stocking density just before being moved to the grow out barns in addition to just before reaching market age, whereas the stocking density will gradually increase from day one and only peak just before market age for birds that are kept in the same building throughout the production cycle.

Commercial flocks are always reared following an all-in-all-out system. However, to optimize the use of the barns in some countries multi-age farms are still present. A typical case is represented by the so called "18 weeks system" in Germany. In this system, male and female poults are placed on the same day in different barns. The hens are sent to slaughter at 15 weeks, and 3 weeks later a new flock of male and female poults are placed, while the males of the previous production cycle (although placed in a different barn) are still on the farm. This system permits better use of the square meters of the farm but obviously has its turnback in a reduction of biosecurity and is likely to be abandoned due to the recent severe outbreaks of avian influenza.

There are no EU legal provisions for stocking density in keeping turkeys except for the general indications of Council Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes. At point 7 of the annex to the directive it is stated that; "The freedom of movement of an animal, having regard to its species and in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge, must not be restricted in such a way as to cause it unnecessary suffering or injury". Stocking densities used throughout Europe are based on

industry guidance (table 9) and are in line with the recommendations of Avec. However, National legislation in Austria, Denmark, Norway, Poland, Sweden and Switzerland provides specific figures.

The most common farming system is Intensive indoor, with different final stocking densities. Some countries also adopt other types of farming systems: 7 countries rear turkeys in organic systems (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Netherlands and Norway) with variable stocking densities, ranging from 25 kg/m² to 10 kg/m². Germany, Netherlands and Switzerland use also the covered verandas farming system: in the case of Germany, birds are reared in these systems at lower densities (43,5 kg/m²) than in intensive indoor systems, while Switzerland only breeds with this system, at maximum densities of 36,5 kg/m² (table 9).

Table 9. Survey answers by turkey experts regarding farming system, stocking density and management procedures applied.

Country	Farming system	Stocking density (kg/m ²)	Brood and move system	Thinning
Austria	Intensive indoor, organic	40 (intensive indoor), 10 (organic)	Yes	Yes
Belgium	Intensive indoor	40 - 50	Yes	Yes
Bulgaria	Intensive indoor	Unknown	No	No
Cyprus	Intensive indoor	32	No	Yes
Denmark	Intensive indoor	55 (Tom) - 52 (Hen)	Yes	No
Finland	Intensive indoor	57	No	No
France	Intensive indoor, organic	55-60	No	Yes
Germany	Intensive indoor; semi-intensive indoor; covered verandas; organic	58 (Tom) 52 (Hen) - (intensive indoor); 53 (Tom) 48 (Hen) - (semi-intensive); 45 (Tom) 42 (Hen) - (verandas); 25 (organic)	No (in case of 19/24 week cycle) - Yes (in case of 13 week cycle)	No
Great Britain	Intensive indoor; Organic; free range	58 (Tom) 42 (Hen) - (intensive indoor); 25 (organic); 25 (free range)	No	No
Hungary	Intensive indoor	50-60	Yes (65 - 70% of total farms)	No
Italy	Intensive indoor, organic	62 (intensive indoor); 21 (organic)	No	Yes - only in low farm density areas
Netherlands	Intensive indoor, covered verandas, organic	45 (intensive indoor)	No (Hen) - Yes (Tom)	No
Norway	Intensive indoor, organic	44 (Tom), 38 (Hen) - intensive indoor	No	No
Poland	Intensive indoor	55	Yes	Yes
Romania	Intensive indoor	46,5 (Tom); 42,5 (Hen)	Yes	Yes
Spain	Intensive indoor	65	No (mostly) - Yes (2 companies)	Yes (Hen)
Sweden	Intensive indoor	45 (Tom), 40 (Hen)	No (50%) - Yes (50%)	No

Switzerland Covered verandas 36,5 No (50%) - Yes (50%) Yes (mostly)

As shown in table 10, some countries responding to the survey, report the use of various types of enrichments during both start and rearing period. The most common type of enrichment used is straw bales. Some countries also use elevated platforms and edible (e.g., pecking stones, hay, alfalfa) or non-edible materials (e.g., chains, plastic bales/bottles). Furthermore, taking Austria as an example, which uses wintergarden as environmental enrichment, it can be seen that maximum stocking densities are reduced to around 40 kg/m², compared to 50-60 kg/m² in some major European turkey producing countries (e.g. Poland and Germany 55kg/m²).

Table 10. Survey results about use of enrichments among European countries.

Country	Use of enrichment	Type of enrichment
Austria	Yes	Straw balls, raised platforms, wintergarden
Belgium	Yes	Staw vales, perches
Bulgaria	No	
Cyprus	Yes	Straw balls, water bottles
Denmark	No	
Finland	Yes	Perches, toys, straw, elevated platforms
France	No	
Germany	Yes	Edible organic material, non edible material, elevated platforms
Great Britain	Yes	Elevated platforms, straw bales, hanging objects
Hungary	No	
Italy	Yes	Toys or strings hanging from the roof, toys on the ground, straw/hay bales,
Netherlands	Yes	Alfaalfa, empty cannisters/bottles, CD's
Norway	Yes	Lucerne common, vegetables
Poland	No	
Romania	No	
Spain	No	
Sweden	No	
Switzerland	Yes	Elevated platforms, straw bales, pecking materials, grit, CD's, water bottles

3.2.3 Turkey breeders

Turkey breeders are the parent and earlier generations (e.g., grandparents, great grandparents) of the commercially used turkeys (broiler turkeys for meat production). Turkey breeding consists of selecting animals of pure lines with a blend of various desired characteristics, mating the selected animals with the selected birds of another pure line, rearing and crossing the F1's with other F1's, and continuing for more generations until the male and the female turkey parent lines, respectively, are mated to produce the commercial turkey. Breeding programmes are developed to respond to the needs of farmers and the market. The selection goals of efficient and fast growth rates and gain of breast meat in turkeys are negatively correlated with fertility. In the Europe, parent stock is kept in loose housing systems on litter. Turkey parent breeders are kept for the production of fertilised eggs from which the commercial turkey poults hatch. Most European turkey producing countries rear commercial turkeys and parent stock while very few rear earlier generations. Parent stock in breeding facilities is kept for a minimum of 56 weeks, and thus these birds have a significantly longer life than broiler turkeys.

After hatch breeder poults, should be confined to an area where feed, water and heat are readily available. This can be done by using a variety of brooder set-ups as described for the commercial birds. The actual brooder ring setup will vary depending on house, stove type, brooding equipment, company preference and the time of year. As the turkeys grow, they will be provided with additional space following the suggested floor space recommendations of the primary breeder guidelines. Consideration must be given to litter type and time of year.

Space recommendations given as bird per square meter are as follow:

- 0-8 weeks of age 7,0 females or 5,5 males
- 9 weeks-selection 4,5 females or 2,0 males
- selection-29 weeks 3,0 females or 1,0 males
- 29 weeks to end: 1,5 females or 1,0 males

Both male and female parent stock are kept in loose housing systems on litter before and after production starts. Up to 29 weeks of age, birds are kept in rearing farms from which they are then transferred to laying farms which are generally rather close. The production cycle of turkey breeders lasts generally a minimum of 24 weeks (laying cycle period).

Breeding is based on artificial insemination (AI). This is practiced because natural mating is difficult for the heavy toms and puts the hens at risk of injury (Wageningen UR Livestock Research, 2010). Furthermore, with AI the number of females that a male can "serve" with the semen he produces is certainly greater than what happens in natural breeding (roughly one male every 5 females). In the case of AI, one male can serve up to 20 – 22 females, achieving at the same time higher fertility levels.

Males are raised in the first phase of their life (0 – 29 weeks) in light-controlled facilities. Generally, the light program for males is very simple: from the second week of life until the end of their career as sperm donors

they are kept at 14 hours of light and 10 hours of darkness with a light intensity of approximately 50 lux. At week 28 the males begin to be "massaged" to check if they provide semen and to evaluate its quality. At 29 weeks they are then moved to the laying farms where they are kept together in floor pens. Semen collection is performed getting semen from several birds (pool semen) generally mixed with specific extender/diluent in connection with insemination of the hens. Males are milked once or twice per week during all their production life.

Sexual maturity in turkey females is reached at around 29 weeks of age. Females in the first phase of their life (0 – 29 weeks) are raised in barns that can guarantee absolute darkness (dark houses). Up to 18 - 19 weeks, females have 14 hours of light and 10 hours of darkness per day, while from 18 -19 until week 29 the hours of light go to 6/7 (with darkness therefore being 17/18 hours). During this part of the bird's life light intensity is generally around 50 lux. At 29 weeks, the females are moved to the laying farms where the hours of light pass from 6/7 to 14 (with 10 hours of darkness) and a minimum of 120 lux and this light stimulation triggers the physiological development of the females into breeders, with the acquisition of weight and oviduct development. Generally, 12 – 13 days after light stimulation the first eggs appear and after 16 – 18 days the females are inseminated for the first time (the lighter lines are inseminated earlier than the heavier ones). Generally, they are inseminated 3 times in the first 8 days and then move on to one insemination per week. The females will lay approximately 110 eggs during the following laying cycle period of approximately 24 weeks.

3.2.4 Slaughterhouses

From the survey results, showed in table 11, it appeared that almost all the turkeys produced in Europe are slaughtered in the main turkey producing countries. All the turkeys produced in Denmark and the Netherlands (with the exception of a very small number slaughtered locally) are slaughtered abroad confirming what was reported in the recent EFSA Technical report of the NCP network. Also, Hungary and Belgium send some turkeys abroad for slaughter and as in the case of Denmark and the Netherlands the slaughter plants of destination are mainly in Germany. The most widespread stunning system is the electric stunning (waterbath), but gas stunning systems are also present in most of the major turkey producing countries. Indeed, in countries such as Germany, Spain, Great Britain, Norway, Romania, Austria and Switzerland gas is the preferred stunning system.

Table 11. Survey results on slaughter plants and stunning systems used among European countries.

Country	N° of slaughter plants	Birds slaughtered/week	Stunning systems
Austria	1	20.000	Gas
Belgium	1	15.000	Electric
Bulgaria	2	150	Electric
Cyprus	4*	3.000 - 6.000	Electric
Denmark	0**	0	
Finland	1	18.000	Electric
France	10	615.384	Electric (main); Gas
Germany	4	635.000	Gas
Great Britain	9	269.230	Gas (main); electric
Hungary	5	127.700	Electric
Italy	4	510.000	Electric; Gas
Netherlands	1***	100	Electric
Norway	2	170.000	Gas
Poland	15	800.000	Electric; one with Gas
Romania	1	25.000	Gas
Spain	7	553.000	Gas (Main); Electric
Sweden	2	9.300	Electric
Switzerland	2	5.500	Gas (main); Electric
Total	66	3.779.364	

*Slaughters dedicated to broilers, slaughtering turkeys only for the Christmas period. **All turkeys are exported to Germany for slaughter. ***One small slaughterhouse, working one day/week.